

MOVARAUNNAKHR'S HISTORY AS A COMMERCIAL AND ECONOMIC CENTER OF THE TIMURID KINGDOM.

Rayimova Sadoqatkhan Azizbek kizi
Fergana State University, lecturer of the
Department of History of Uzbekistan
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Abstract: The article examines the economic policy of Amir Temur's powerful and huge state and its role in the life of the peoples of Central Asia. We know that the era of Amir Temur and the Timurids in the 14th-15th centuries is a "golden age" as a period of renaissance in the history of Central Asia. Currently, the formation of a national economic idea for the economic stability of the country has always been considered an urgent issue. In this article, Amir Temur and The conditions created for the development of external and internal trade relations within the framework of the economic reforms during the Timurid period are analyzed, and at the same time, the importance of fundamental changes in the socio-economic life of our country is shown. It is a fundamental basis for the further development of our thinking, and its practical use will undoubtedly make a significant contribution to the economic growth of our country.

Key words: Amir Temur, trade-monetary relations, crafts, trade, economic and cultural relations during the Timurid period

It is known that our national statehood has a thousand-year history and is certainly rich has culture. Therefore, foreign economic and trade-monetary relations are closely connected with the deepest layers of our history. In particular, it is no exaggeration to say that he paved the way for the development of trade and commodity-money relations, which play an important role in the economic life of the country. Especially during the period of Amir Temur, the commercial and cultural development of Mowarunnam, the center of his great government, developed steadily. That is why the period of the Timurids, that is, the period of renaissance in the 14th-15th centuries, is also called the "golden age" in the history of Central Asia. The economic environment of Movarunnahr in the 14th-15th centuries. The topographic appearance of Shahrisabz, Karshi, Tashkent and many other cities has changed radically, and the professional, internal and external relations of their inhabitants have also developed rapidly. As a result of intensive trade, economic and cultural relations with different countries, new types of handicrafts have appeared. , individual goods began to be sold on the counters of specialized markets in the city of Samarkand. The unique features of this market surprised everyone. In his memoirs, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur emphasized that there were special trade facilities in Samarkand during the time of Amir Temur. He writes: "...this shaham has a quality that cannot be found anywhere else. Each craftsman has a specialized market and relies on each other's mood and attitude. Except for the "buzurg" (prime minister) in the state administration of the Amir

each province had departments called "divan". They were in charge of public affairs, such as collecting taxes, maintaining order, controlling buildings, markets, baths, roads, and water points. Devon officials were responsible for the peaceful life of the people. Therefore, they

studied the accuracy of the scales in the markets, the fairness of the price. Prices of goods are calculated at the currency exchange office located in the central market. Strict action was taken against the suppliers who increased the price, and the interests of consumers were protected². At that time, swindlers and merchants who committed fraud were stopped and punished in the market, in front of the society. Trade-money during the time of Amir Temur It would not be wrong to say that since the time of Amir Temur, the principles of transparency and the foundations of civilized democracy began to appear. Importers are allowed to increase the price of goods by up to ten percent in order to protect the population from monopoly in the market.

Consequently, the domestic consumer markets were filled with the best quality, brightest and most importantly, the cheapest products. 3. Our great grandfather Sahinqiron Amir Temur and his successors paid great attention to the expansion of trade activities in our country. Caravanserai were built on all the caravan routes that passed through the provinces and regions of the state. Amir Temur for a one-day caravan to develop trade relations

ordered that all the necessary conditions should be provided, namely horses, fodder, food, caravanserais and sardb (thirst-satisfying place), that robbers should be severely punished and that sellers should be taken care of. The following line can be read in Temuming's work "The Laws of Timur": "I appointed merchants and soldiers in every country, Khotan, Chin Mochin (China), India, Arab countries, Egypt, Sham, Rum, Algeria, Farangistan (France), wherever they go, let them bring their fine cloths and beautiful gifts. Let them tell of the condition of the people who live in these countries, and how the rulers of each country treat their people and their race. "Also, I will tell the observers and the representatives of the law. I ordered them to monitor the roads, follow passengers, merchants, foreigners, and help in transporting my family's property and other things to their destination. If there is a murder or other incident, they take responsibility for what happened on the road

they should receive."⁴ "If there are 1/6 cases of loss, I ordered the sellers to take their funds with a sufficient amount of gold at the expense of the state" 5. As a result of the implementation of these measures, the number of caravan routes increased stable domestic and foreign trade has developed. Movarunnahr important role in commodity exchange and trade. Amir Temur believed that the world will be prosperous thanks to sellers. Accordingly, roads and trade networks

invested a lot of money in its creation. At the same time, political and economic relations with the Middle East and the Far East, as well as European countries such as Spain, France and England, were expanding. In particular, regular trade was conducted with China, India, Iran, Russia, Volga and Siberia. Amir Temur's involvement in economic reforms. From Samarkand to foreign countries, in particular, to Russia, Tatarstan, Siberia, cheap yarn, silk, cotton and finished yarn, paper, dried fruits, and rice were sent. Spanish Ambassador Ruy González de Clavijo says in his diary that Samarkand took a high place in foreign trade: "Leather and painted gloves from Russia (Russia) and Tatarstan, the most beautiful luxury fabrics from China, satin fabrics, as well as musk, rubies, diamonds, in particular, several things that could only be procured in China, pearls, rhubarb, and many different aromatic and medicinal herbs were brought in. From India the finest aromatic spices, nutmeg, peppermint, cinnamon dyes and even goods not given to the Kingdom of Alexandria were brought to Samarkand". Claviho describes Samarkand as one of the richest cities in the world: "This land is rich in everything, grain, wine,

rich in fruit, poultry and animal meat, livestock was very large. Their fat tails were heavy enough to carry in their hands, each sheep's fat tail weighed eight to ten kilograms. There were a lot of them and they were very cheap, when the Tsar's army gathered in Samarkand, the price of a pair of these sheep was "ducat" (gold coins minted in Spain). Other goods were also very cheap, barley for one and a half "dara" (the weight of grain used in crops in Spain) costing almost half a "real" (Spanish currency). Water for bread was free, and rice was found in every market. The melons of this land were juicy and sweet. Many camels loaded with melons came every day, and it was impossible not to think about where and how to buy and eat so many melons. Samarkand and its surrounding lands were surprisingly rich. The city was called "Semizkent" because of its wealth. Its real name means "rich village". Samarkand comes from this name. The wealth of the city is not only rich and cheap food, but royal fabrics such as Atlas, silk, sandal, taffeta and fur, as well as many other things such as perfumes and other cosmetics, spices, resins, coke dyes, etc. there were".⁷ In the memoirs of Claviho's travels, many facts are given about large gardens and shopping areas: "Every year in the city of Samarkand (referring to the capital of Movaraunnahr) goods imported from India, China, the Golden Horde were sold. Until that time, there was not much place to sell all the goods delivered to the city. The king ordered to build a street with markets on both sides. This street had to start at one end and cross the middle to exit at the other end of the city. The ruler assigned this work to two generals. They knew very well that for this they had to work tirelessly day and night and answer with their own heads. The houses standing on the road were destroyed, evicted... Streets

on either side were bazaars with marble benches in front of each shop. The shops consisted of two rooms. The top of the street was covered with domes (tim) and it consisted of small openings through which daylight entered. By the time the construction was completed, the market was filled with traders. In June of the same year (1404), "a trade caravan of eight hundred camels arrived in Samarkand from the city of Kambalek (Hanoi, Beijing)" ⁸. As the Spanish ambassador noted, "the ruler on the occasion of a big wedding. "The trade of the city of Samarkand people dealing with foreign exchange (sarraf), sellers of cotton fabrics (chitfurush), jewelry and various goods, cooks, butchers, bakers and craftsmen from other cities were allowed to go to the central square of the ruler and build tents for trade and organize a fair.

after that, all the merchants and sellers who left the city had to come to the central square, and every craftsman had to organize entertaining performances for the people*. It is worth mentioning that Jan (Ioann, also called Ioann de Galonifontibus in some sources) was the ambassador of Amir Timur of the Sultanate of Iran. His memoirs entitled "Memoires sur sur tamerlan et sa cour" (Memoires sur sur tamerlan et sa cour) have taken an important place as a reliable and impartial source among more than a thousand works created during the last six hundred years. It is considered one of the rarest works and is valuable because it is alongside the works of historical authors such as Ibn Arabshah, Ibn Khaldun and the European ambassador Claviho, who were personally and closely related to Amir Timur. Also of this asaming "Trading in the section of Timur's kingdom and his city rule

states the following confession about his relations: During his reign, he canceled the taxes for soul and salt in many areas and ordered to collect them only in small cities. On the territory of his state, he punished those who threatened the lives of merchants and harmed Targovs the inhabitants of the countries had to deliver or they were charged a fine in the amount of 3/6 of what was lost.

It is valuable because it is alongside the works of historical authors such as Ibn Arabshah, Ibn Khaldun and the European ambassador Clavijo. In addition, the following recognition of trade relations in the section of "Timur's reign and his city rule" of this work is stated: During his reign, he canceled the taxes for soul and salt in many areas and ordered to collect them only in large cities. severely punished those who threatened their lives: the inhabitants of the countries that damaged the targos had to pay double the amount of the damage caused or a fine of five times the amount of the lost property was collected." Trade-money relations during the Timurid period. The embassies established by the Timurids played an important role in expanding trade with foreign countries. In the first quarter of the 15th century, Amir Temur's son Shahrukh and his grandson Ulugbek regularly exchanged ambassadors between their countries and China. Mirza Ulughbek managed the city of Movarunnahr perfectly, in particular, he conducted foreign policy as the great leader wanted. If there was any question related to foreign and domestic policy, he would always talk to Sahibgiron Amir Temur and get his approval. Naturally, China was interested in trading with the Timurids. Horses were brought to this country mainly from Mowarunnahr and Khurasan. At that time, trade-mediation relations and the activities of embassies were very developed. Once in two or three years, Samarkand merchants and ambassadors regularly went to China (Beijing), and Chinese merchants regularly went to Samarkand and Herat. In 1418, Shahrukh and Ardasher were ambassadors to China. The following year, Lee Diva Chong-ku came to Samarkand and Herat as an ambassador from China. They are

They brought letters and expensive gifts to Shahrukh and Ulugbek as a symbol of strengthening their friendly relations. In 1420, Shahrukh and Ulug'bek went to China with an embassy convoy of 530 people. Two caravan routes were opened from Movarunnahr to China. The first is through the cities of Tashkent, Sayram, Yettisuv, Turfon (Eastern Turkestan) and Kumul, and the second is through the cities of Khojand, Kokan, Margilan, Andijan, Osh, Oloy Valley and Kashkar, Khotan in the Fergana Valley. and cities. Special attention is paid to the safety of these roads. Neighborly relations with Tibet and India were also established during the reign of Shahrukh and Ulugbek. In the first half of the 15th century, the economic prosperity of the country, especially the development of crafts and internal trade, depended to a large extent on the ongoing monetary reforms. During the reign of Amir Temur, money was minted in forty cities, especially in Samarkand, and a quarter of the income was allocated to the state treasury. In the historical chronology, receipts were given to the military in case of lack of funds. 11 First, Amir Temur, then the Timurids introduced currency in the country. Amir Temur ordered the minting of six-gram "coins" and half-gram silver coins, which were called "mini". They were named "Suyug'rgatmish" and "Sultan Mahmud Khan" and were minted in more than 40 major cities of Movarunnahr, Khorasan, Iran, Azerbaijan and Iraq. Shahrukh Mirza, as the commander of Movarunnahr and Khurasan, ordered the minting of silver coins in cities such as Astrobad, Bukhara, Domgon, Isfahan, Kushan, Kermon, Qum, Nishapur, Marv, Samarkand, Sabzavor, Sultan. He founded money production in Tabriz, Khorezm, Herat, Shiraz and other cities, thereby regulating

internal trade. Small copper coins "fulus" minted by local governors were widely used in domestic retail trade. The introduction of a single currency in the country, the regulation of money circulation, of course, domestic and foreign trade

served for the further development of relations. From this point of view, Ulugbek's reform of "fulus" money in 1428 was of great importance. Ulugbek banned all small and light money in circulation in order to attract the population to domestic retail trade. In order to meet the demand for small copper coins, special mints were opened in Bukhara, Samarkand, Karshi, Termiz, Tashkent, Shokhrukhiya and Andijan. "Fulus" of the same weight entered circulation there. In a short time, the old coins were replaced with new fulus, mints were stopped in order to centralize money circulation, and only one was left in Bukhara. Mirzo Ulugbek was popularly known as "fulusi adliya", i.e. "fair coin". Another important information: Ulugbek aims to increase foreign trade revenues.

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In conclusion, it can be said that Amir Temur is equal within a certain period of time was able to create an unprecedentedly huge state, despite 3.5 and even 7 years of war, he was able to maintain peace and economic stability in the country. Movaraunnammi, developing both foreign and domestic trade was able to turn it into a perfect shopping center. This indicates the strong intellectual potential and scientific knowledge of Sahibqiran and is a real proof that the state has reached the highest economic peak.

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